

UZBEKISTAN'S MEMBERSHIP IN THE WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION: PROBLEMS AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Annotation: In this article about the role of organization the World Trade Organization is, the legal procedure for membership in the organization, the system of legal norms in the management of international trade by the organization, the advantages and disadvantages of the organization for countries, as well as the legal study of Uzbekistan's membership in this organization.

Keywords: World Trade Organization, membership, antidumping, GATT, GATS, TRIPS, TRIMS, protectionism, the principle of national regime.

INTRODACTION: The results of the analysis of the processes taking place in the world economy show that the liberalization of foreign trade is becoming one of the main trends in the development of the world economy. All countries are witnessing the reduction of customs duties and the abolition of many types of restrictions. Many countries also covertly use protectionist measures.

These measures include providing subsidies to national production types, subsidizing exports, introducing various norms and standards, and others. International economic organizations, in particular, the World Trade Organization (WTO), play an important role in solving the conflicts between free trade and protectionism in the world economy, managing international trade, eliminating and liberalizing obstacles to its development. In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-4947, five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 The action strategy has been approved. Paragraph 3.1 of this strategy includes further development of international economic cooperation in order to further strengthen macroeconomic stability and maintain high economic growth rates, including expanding relations with leading international and foreign financial institutions, continuing to implement a well-thought-out foreign debt policy , it was established that the foreign investments and loans involved should be used effectively¹.

In the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 24, 2018 No. 1040 "On approval of the composition of the Interagency Commission on working with the World Trade Organization", the process of the entry of the Republic of Uzbekistan into the World Trade Organization is effectively organized. In order to ensure coordination on a systematic basis, the Inter-Departmental Commission on working with the World Trade Organization was approved².

The importance of the World Trade Organization to countries and world trade has been studied to a considerable extent. Because of this, although this organization was established in 1994, its original form, GATT, was established in 1947. For this reason, many scientific studies have been conducted by scientists.

In particular, our local scientists G.Yuldasheva, M.Kh.Vokhidova; Sh. Khajibakiev, as well as foreign scientists E. Petersmann, M. Herdegen, I.V. Zenkin conducted scientific research.

Also, the specification of the topic in the research required the use of systematic-structural, dialectical, logical, formal-legal, comparative-legal, historical-legal and comparative-typological methods of analysis.

General logical methods - induction, deduction, analysis, synthesis and special legal methods were used. The method of grammatical analysis was also used in the interpretation of scientific literature and legal norms. Scientific observation, systematic and economic-statistical analysis, comparison and grouping methods were used in the research.

1 Action strategy for the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017. <https://lex.uz/docs/-3107036>

2 The composition of the Interagency Commission on working with the World Trade Organization, approved by the Cabinet of Ministers' decision No. 1040 of December 24, 2018. <https://lex.uz/docs/-4124260>

WTO membership is complex in nature and affects all sectors of the economy and not only the country's foreign trade regime (customs rates, technical regulations, sanitary and phytosanitary measures, etc.), agriculture (agriculture state support), economy, price regulation, etc.), will also make changes to the regulation of intellectual property, services (services of foreign companies), state orders, state regulation of the economy, etc.

The international community, including the main trade partners of our country, supports Uzbekistan's more open participation in world trade and fully supports Uzbekistan's WTO membership process. In particular, the European Union allocated a grant of 5 million euros to finance the process of becoming a member of the World Trade Organization (WTO). The agreement between the parties was signed in Brussels on November 11, 2019, and provides assistance to Uzbekistan in the process of becoming a member of the World Trade Organization, including in the preparation of necessary documents, and in improving the knowledge of Uzbek experts on WTO agreements. implies.

Membership of countries in the WTO serves as the main factor of economic development in these countries and elimination of monopoly in the country. Although it has been more than 25 years since the Republic of Uzbekistan applied for WTO membership, this process is still ongoing. If we look at history, it takes 4-15 years for other countries to join the WTO. Therefore, it is necessary to develop specific measures to identify the problems that prevent Uzbekistan from becoming a member of this country and to eliminate them.

The peculiarity of the WTO is that the organization promotes trade by gradually liberalizing the trade practices of its member states, creating more opportunities for competition and the efficiency of trade exchanges between countries. I.A. Khamedov and A.M. As noted by Alimov, the organization ensures non-discriminatory trade between member states, supports transparency and predictability of trade practices, and resolves trade disputes between members. Countries join the World Trade Organization in order to take advantage of free trade opportunities and to use the WTO's integrated dispute resolution mechanism, which in turn is one of the main reasons why our country is a member of this organization.

As a result of Uzbekistan's membership in this organization, a systematic analysis of the expected changes in the legislation of Uzbekistan and unification with international norms will prevent disputes that may arise in the future and limit excessive confusion.

It is expected to study the extent to which the changes in the international legal status of Uzbekistan as a result of WTO membership and the expected changes in trade and other types of relations with other countries will affect the current situation of Uzbekistan. is a guarantee of prevention and elimination of problems. For this reason, it is not allowed to be squeezed out of the domestic market. Also, only in this case, the reduction of trade restrictions will undoubtedly increase business activity, attract investments and help the country join international value chains, which will be reflected in the further modernization and growth of the country's economic indicators.

Based on the above, taking into account the future admission of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the WTO, the following is proposed: in order for goods and products to have the right to enter the market, the WTO member countries must not increase the maximum duty rates specified in the Tariff List (Schedule of Concession) regulated by Article II of the GATT - 1994. In addition, WTO members are strictly prohibited from applying quantitative restrictions on the entry of goods and products into the market. Also, WTO member countries should not allow non-tariff barriers (such as customs clearance procedures) to become excessive barriers to trade.

Therefore, the Customs Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan should be revised. In particular, it is appropriate to revise the articles of this Code that give the right to set the following quantitative restrictions:

-I- Article 54 (the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan may set quantitative restrictions on allowing processing of goods in the customs regime of processing outside the customs territory);

-I- Article 82 (the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan may set quantitative restrictions on placing goods under the customs regime of processing in the customs territory);
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-I- Article 364 (when importing goods into the customs territory, the certificate of origin of the goods is provided in a mandatory manner for goods whose import from a certain country is controlled by quantitative restrictions (quotas) or other measures of regulation of foreign economic activity);

-I- Chapter 43 of the Customs Code, known as preferences and tariff preferences for the payment of customs fees, should be revised based on the principle of the most favorable regime and the principle of the national regime.

The anti-dumping agreement also details the rules for the initiation and implementation of anti-dumping investigations by inspection bodies of WTO member states. Article 12 of the Anti-Dumping Agreement also specifies the obligation to inform the competent authority about the anti-dumping investigation and publish the results of the investigation. In addition, Article 13 of the Anti-Dumping Agreement requires the existence of independent courts, arbitral tribunals or administrative tribunals and procedures for review of findings or final findings in anti-dumping proceedings.

Conclusion: Our legislation stipulates that these types of disputes will be considered by administrative courts. Therefore, in order to implement the provisions of the Anti-Dumping Agreement, we need to introduce in our legislation the procedure for reviewing disputes related to anti-dumping in arbitration courts.

In addition, it is necessary to take measures to eliminate the investment restrictions existing in our legislation, for this purpose, it is necessary to revise the prohibited areas of investment in

the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Special Economic Zones, as well as the regulation of investment relations in our country. It is desirable to adapt the regulatory legal documents to the provisions of the WTO and its TRIMS agreement.

Due to the current instability of opinions and views on the work of the WTO, we, as candidates for membership in this organization, must consider all possible consequences and results of the development of events. However, at the same time, the very idea of changing the country's trade system due to changes in world trade positions can have a positive effect on the national system of trade regulation.

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